

INCREASING THE PRODUCTIVITY OF RICE-RICE AND RICE-WHEAT SYSTEMS BY INCORPORATING MUSTARD AND MUNG BEAN UNDER CONSERVATION AGRICULTURE PRACTICES

M.M. Hossain^{1*}, M. Begum¹, A. Hashem², R.W. Beji³ and M.E. Haque³

¹Department of Agronomy, Bangladesh Agricultural University

²Department of Agriculture and Food, Western Australia

³Murdoch University, Australia

*Corresponding author: shakilmoba@gmail.com

Conservation agriculture (CA) practices based on increased residue retention are being developed in Bangladesh but the productivities of cropping sequence with the inclusion of new crop(s) are still to be assessed. T. aman (summer rice-fallow-boro (winter rice) and T. aman-fallow-wheat are two most dominant cropping patterns of Bangladesh and these patterns need intensification for increasing system productivity and farmers' income. In this experiment, mustard (*Brassica napus*) and mung bean (*Vigna mungo*) are incorporated in this two patterns respectively and compared in four farmers' field at Gouripur upazila under Mymensingh district of Bangladesh during 2013-2014 and 2014-2015. Incorporation of mustard between two rice crops and mungbean between rice and wheat, increased the rice equivalent yield (REY) by 23 and 30% and the gross return by 62 and 66%, respectively. While compared to the existing rice-rice and rice-wheat patterns strip tillage (ST) increased the gross return by 43% over conventional tillage (CT) in rice-rice pattern and 45% by rice-wheat pattern. In double rice pattern, retention of 50% crop residue increased the REY by 4% and gross return by 8% compared to no-residue practice which was 6% and 9% higher, respectively in rice-wheat pattern. Experimental evidence reveals that, inclusion of mustard in rice-rice and mungbean in rice-wheat pattern increased the system productivity and farmers thus could be benefited more by adopting CA practices.

